

Possible Antiamoebic Agents. Part XX. Synthesis of New Biguanide Derivatives

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Several new biguanides, based on the partial structure of chlorhexidine, have been synthesized as possible antiamoebic agents.

Recent routine pharmacological screenings [*in vitro* and *in vivo* (rats) against *E. histolytica*] have revealed chlorhexidine¹ (I), a well known antiseptic, to be a highly active amoebicide, being twice as active as emetine and a 100% cysticide, without imparting any toxic effect².

It is noteworthy that now well known as amoebicides, yatren and vioform, were also introduced originally as antiseptics. The other most important feature of this compound is the presence of the *p*-chlorophenylbiguanide grouping of the well-known antimalarial, chloroguanide (Paludrin).

In the present investigation, the syntheses of a number of biguanide derivatives, based on the partial structure of chlorhexidine, have been undertaken with a view to ascertaining the effect of simplification of the chlorhexidine molecule on amoebicidal activity. The following types of compounds have been prepared:

- (I) *N*¹-*p*-Iodophenyl-*N*³-dialkylaminopropyl^{1a} biguanide dihydrochlorides.
- (II) *N*¹-Arylcarbamylbiguanide hydrochlorides.
- (III) *N*¹-Arylthiocarbamyl-*N*³-arylbiquanide hydrochlorides.
- (IV) *N*¹-Arylsulphonyl-*N*³-arylbiquanide hydrochlorides.
- (V) *N*¹*N*³-Diarylbiquanide hydrochlorides.

2,5-Dimethoxy- and 3,4-dimethoxy-anilines have been prepared by reduction of the corresponding nitrobenzenes with Raney nickel and palladised charcoal, respectively.

1. Rose and Swain, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 4422.

2. B. N. Singh, *private communication*.

(1) Compound of type (I) were obtained by refluxing equimolecular quantities of *p*-iodophenyldicyandiamide and appropriate γ -dialkylaminopropylamine with ethanol (95%), after addition of HCl (conc.) to it.

(2) Compounds of type (II) having an additional-C=O grouping were prepared for the first time by two different methods. The following steps are involved:

(3) Compounds of type(III) were prepared for the first time by refluxing appropriate arylthiocarbamyl dicyandiamide with arylamine hydrochloride in aqueous dimethyl formamide. The former were obtained by condensing sodium arylthiocarbamyl acetate with dicyandiamide. The following steps are involved:

(4) The high antiameobic activity of the thiazolidone dioxides³ and the discovery that the introduction of -SO₂- grouping enhances amoebacidal activity of certain dichloroacetanilides⁴ prompted the synthesis of compounds of type (IV) by refluxing appropriate arylsulphonyl dicyandiamide with different arylamine hydrochlorides in a aqueous solution. The arylsulphonyl dicyandiamides in turn were obtained for the first time by the action of appropriate arylsulphonyl chloride on dicyandiamide in aqueous solution. The steps

3. Surrey *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 578.

4. Kidd and Wright, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 1420.

involved are:

(5) *N'**N*'-Diarylbiguanido hydrochlorides with two aryl moieties (as in I) linked to one biguanide chain were prepared by refluxing appropriate arylamine hydrochloride and aqueous dicyanamide solution containing hydrochloric acid, according to following scheme:

EXPERIMENTAL

p-Iodophenyldicyandiamide.—*p*-Iodoaniline (21.9g., 0.1*M*) was dissolved in hydrochloric acid (2.5*N*, 100 ml) and diazotised with sodium nitrite (7g., 0.1*M*, dissolved in 40 ml water) at 0-5°. The solution was filtered and added with stirring to dicyandiamide (9.2g., 0.11*M*), suspended in water (100 ml) below 20°. Excess of NaOH solution (10*N*) was added to make the medium alkaline. Stirring was continued for further 30 mins. The yellow solution was acidified with acetic acid (glacial). The precipitated triazine was filtered and washed with water. It was then added portionwise during 15 mins. to a mixture of acetone (100 ml) and HCl (conc., 10 ml) with stirring at 30-40°. Brisk evolution of nitrogen ensued. When no more N₂ had evolved (1 hour), water (200 ml) was added and the precipitate was filtered which was redissolved in hot 1*N*-NaOH (100 ml), treated with animal charcoal, filtered, and reprecipitated with HCl (conc.). The solid was filtered and recrystallised from 95% ethanol, yield 10 g. (35%), m.p. 220° (lit⁵. m.p. 222°). *Picrate* m.p. 170°. (Found: N, 18.90. C₁₄H₁₀O₇N₇I requires N, 19.00%).

N'-*p*-Iodophenyl-*N*'-dialkylaminopropyl⁶biguanide Dihydrochloride.—*p*-Iodo phenyldicyandiamide (0.01*M*), appropriate γ -dialkylaminopropylamine (0.01*M*) and absolute ethanol (20 ml) were refluxed for 8 hours after addition of HCl (conc., 5ml) to it. The solution was allowed to stand overnight and the crystals separating were filtered and recrystallised from ethanol. Their yields, m.p.s and analyses are reported in Table I.

TABLE I

-N $\begin{array}{l} \text{R}' \\ \diagup \\ \text{R}'' \end{array}$	Yield.	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.
			I-		
-N(Me) ₂	35%	217°	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ N ₆ Cl ₂ I	18.10	18.22
-N(Et) ₂	40	126°	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₆ Cl ₂ I	17.00	17.17
	45	218°	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₆ Cl ₂ I	16.58	16.76
	40	215°	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ ON ₆ Cl ₂ I	16.60	16.70

5. Curd et al., *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 1634.

N'-*p*-Iodophenyl-*N*³-benzylbiguanide Hydrochloride. — *p*-Iodophenyldicyandiamide (1.4 g.) and benzylamine (0.5 ml) were refluxed with ethanol (10 ml) and hydrochloric acid (1 ml) for 8 hours. The separated crystals were filtered and recrystallised from ethanol, yield 0.8 g. (38%), m.p. 126°. (Found: N, 16.1. C₁₃H₁₇N₅ClI requires N, 16.31%).

N'-Arylcarmamylbiguanide Hydrochlorides: *Method A*.—Appropriate monoarylyurea and dicyandiamide (0.1*M* each) were refluxed with ethanol (95%, 50 ml) for 12-16 hours after addition of HCl (conc., 5 ml). The solution was concentrated to half its volume and left overnight. The separated crystals were filtered and repeatedly recrystallised from ethanol to yield the pure product.

Method B.—In another experiment, the reactants were heated to 170-80° when melting occurred and a clear solution was obtained. HCl (conc., 1 ml) was then added to it. Within 5 mins. a solid appeared following a brisk reaction. 2*N*-HCl(5ml) was added after cooling it and the mixture boiled. It was filtered hot and the solid thus obtained was recrystallised from aqueous dimethylformamide.

Method C.—Urea nitrate (15.5 g., 0.125*M*), dicyandiamide (8.5 g., 0.1*M*), and water (50 ml) were refluxed for 2 hours. The resulting solution was allowed to stand overnight and crystals separating were filtered and recrystallised from water as white cubical crystals of carbamylbiguanido nitrate

were obtained in 80% yield; m.p. > 280°. (Found: N, 47.14. C₃H₆O₄N₇ requires N, 47.34%).

The free base was obtained by treating it with ammonia solution (*d* 0.888). Recrystallised from ethanol, it melted above 280°. (Found: N, 58.28. C₃H₆ON₆ requires N, 58.33%).

Free base as well as its nitrate furnished the same picrate, m.p. > 280°. (Found: N, 33.68. C₉H₁₁O₈N₉ requires N, 33.78%).

TABLE II

R.	Method.	Yield.	M.P.	Formula,	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.
4-Methyl-	A	15%	*220°	C ₁₀ H ₁₃ ON ₆ Cl	31.00	31.05
	B	35	218°	"	30.86	"
	C	20	220°	"	31.00	"
4-Methoxy-	A	12	> 280°	C ₁₀ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₆ Cl	29.15	2.31
	B	35	> 280°	"	29.00	"
	C	15	> 280°	"	29.04	"
4-Acetyl-amino-	B	40	> 280°	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ C ₆ N ₇ Cl	31.00	31.25
2,4-Dichloro-	B	30	> 280°	C ₉ H ₁₁ ON ₆ Cl ₃	28.68	28.87

*Undepressed when admixed with 1B or C.

Thiocarbamylbiguanide nitrate was similarly prepared from thiourea nitrate and dicyandiamide (0.1*M* each) in 85% yield, m.p. >280°. (Found: N, 43.84. $C_3H_5O_3N_3S$ requires N, 43.99%).

Carbamyl biguanide and *p*-toluidine hydrochloride (0.1*M* each) were refluxed with absolute ethanol (25 ml) for 10 hours after addition of HCl (conc., 5 ml) to it. The mixture was allowed to stand overnight and the crystals separating were filtered and recrystallised repeatedly from ethanol to yield *p*-tolylcarbamylbiguanide hydrochloride; yield 20%, m.p. 220°, undepressed with the product obtained by method A or B. (Found: N, 31.00. $C_{10}H_{15}ON_6Cl$ requires N, 31.05%). *Picrate* m.p. 225°. (Found: N, 27.10. $C_{16}H_{17}O_9N_9$ requires N, 27.22%). The yields, m.p.s and, analyses of these are reported in Table II.

Dimethoxyanilines.—2,5-Dimethoxynitrobenzene (10 g.) was dissolved in ethyl acetate (50 ml) and warmed to gentle boiling. It was reduced catalytically in presence of Raney nickel (1.0 g.) at 60 lbs./p.s. for 5 hours. Catalyst was then filtered and dry HCl gas passed into the filtrate. 2,5-Dimethoxyaniline hydrochloride precipitating was filtered and recrystallised from acetone-ethanol, yield 10g. (97%), m.p. 230°. (Found: N, 7.38. Calc. for $C_8H_{11}O_2NCl$: N, 7.40%). *Picrate* m.p. 173°. (Found: N, 15.25. $C_{14}H_{14}O_9N_4$ requires N, 15.18%).

3,4-Dimethoxynitrobenzene (5 g.) was similarly reduced with palladised charcoal (10%, 0.5g.). 3,4-Dimethoxyaniline hydrochloride was obtained as white needles, yield 4.0g. (80%), m.p. 235°. (Found: N, 7.36. Calc. for $C_8H_{11}O_2NCl$: N, 7.40%). *Picrate* m.p. 175°. (Found: N, 15.30. $C_{14}H_{14}O_9N_4$ requires N, 15.18%).

Arylthiocarbamyl dicyandiamides.—Appropriate arylamine (0.1*M*) was dissolved in ammonia solution (*d* 0.888, 20 ml) and ethanol (20 ml) added to dissolve the amine; CS_2 (4ml) was added dropwise with stirring to it and the solution shaken for an hour. Ammonium aryldithiocarbamate formed was precipitated. To this sodium chloroacetate (0.1*M*) was added and the resulting solution shaken for 15 mins. Dicyandiamide (0.1*M*) was then added to it and the mixture heated on a water bath with occasional stirring for an hour. It was allowed to cool; the crystals separating were filtered and recrystallised from dimethylformamide. The yields, m.p.s, and analyses of these are reported in Table III.

TABLE III

R.	Yield.	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.
4-Methyl-	40%	170°	$C_{10}H_{11}N_5S$	30.00	30.04
4-Methoxy-	50	210°	$C_{10}H_{11}ON_5S$	28.30	28.51
4-Aceto-	55	211°	$C_{11}H_{11}ON_5S$	27.68	27.81
4-Acetylamino-	45	212°	$C_{11}H_{12}ON_5S$	30.27	30.43

*N*¹-Arylthiocarbamyl-*N*⁵-arylbiquanide Hydrochlorides.—Appropriate arylthiocarbamyl dicyandiamide (0.1*M*), arylamine hydrochloride (0.1*M*), and dimethylformamide (50 ml) were refluxed for 8 hours. The solution was allowed to stand overnight and crystals separat-

ing were filtered and recrystallised from aqueous dimethylformamide. The yields, m.p.s, and analyses of these are recorded in Table IV.

TABLE IV

R'.	Yield.	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.
R=4-methyl.					
4-Methyl-	45%	> 280°	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ N ₆ ClS	22.20	22.31
4-Acetylamino-	50	> 280°	C ₁₈ H ₂₃ ON ₆ SCl	23.25	23.36
R=4-methoxy.					
4-Aceto-	50	> 280°	C ₁₈ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₆ ClS	20.45	20.40
4-Methoxy-	50	> 280°	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₆ ClS	20.85	20.58
R=4-aceto.					
4-Aceto-	60	> 280°	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₆ ClS	19.34	19.42
4-Acetylamino-	55	> 280°	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₆ ClS	21.69	21.69
R=4-acetylamino.					
4-Acetylamino-	55	> 280°	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₆ ClS	24.10	24.21
4-Methoxy-	58	> 280°	C ₁₈ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₆ ClS	22.40	22.50

Arylsulphonyldicyandiamides.—Appropriate arylsulphonyl chloride (0.11M), dicyandiamide (0.1M), sodium acetate (0.15M), and water (25 ml) were refluxed for 2 hours. Arylsulphonyl chloride formed a separate layer as it melted in the beginning which gradually disappeared with the completion of the reaction. The resulting solution was allowed to stand overnight and the crystals separating were filtered and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol. The yields, m.p.s, and analyses of these are recorded in Table V.

TABLE V

R.	Yield.	*M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.
4-Methyl-	50%	235°	C ₉ H ₁₀ O ₁ N ₄ S	23.40	23.53
4-Chloro-	45	210°	C ₈ H ₇ O ₂ N ₄ ClS	21.50	21.66
3,4-Dimethoxy-	45	270°	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₄ S	19.54	19.73

*The compounds resolidify after melting. Resolidified products melt > 280°.

N¹-Arylsulphonyl-N³-arylbiquanide Hydrochlorides.—Appropriate arylsulphonyl dicyandiamide and arylamine hydrochloride (0.01M each) were refluxed with water (10 ml) for 10 hours. The resulting solution was allowed to stand overnight and the separated crystals were filtered and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol. Their yields, m.p.s, and analyses are recorded in Table VI.

TABLE VI

R'.	Yield.	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen. Found.	Reqd.
R=4-methyl.					
4-Bromo-	55%	208°	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ BrClS	15.60	15.65
4-Iodo-	50	185°	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ ClIS	14.90	14.18
4-Methoxy-	45	221°	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₃ ClS	17.50	17.61
4-Methyl-	40	> 280°	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₃ ClS	18.28	18.24
R=4-chloro.					
4-Methoxy-	55	165°	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₃ Cl ₂ S	16.60	16.74
4-Iodo-	60	201°	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₃ Cl ₂ IS	17.51	13.61
4-Sulphonic acid	60	> 280°	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₃ Cl ₂ S ₂	14.92	14.95
3,4-Dimethoxy-	48	> 280°	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₃ Cl ₂ S	15.46	15.66
R=3,4-dimethoxy.					
4-Iodo-	56	> 280°	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₃ ClIS	12.87	12.97
2,4-Dichloro-	55	180°	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₃ Cl ₃ S	14.95	14.52
2,5-Dimethoxy-	45	232°	C ₁₈ H ₂₄ O ₆ N ₃ ClS	14.75	14.78
3,4-Dimethoxy-	50	200°	C ₁₈ H ₂₄ O ₆ N ₃ ClS	14.73	14.78

N¹N³-Diarylbiquanide Hydrochlorides.—Calcium cyanamide (10 g.) was allowed to react with cyanogen bromide (10 g. of 50% aqueous solution) at room temperature for 12 hours. The mixture was warmed on a water bath and filtered. To the filtrate appropriate arylamine hydrochloride (0.05M) and HCl (conc., 5 ml) were added and the mixture was refluxed for 8 hours. Hot solution was treated with charcoal, filtered, and allowed to stand overnight. The crystals thus separated were filtered and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol. The yields, m.p.s, and analyses of these are reported in Table VII.

TABLE VII

R.	Yield.	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen. Found.	Reqd.
2-Methoxy-	55%	182°	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	20.21	20.26
2,5-Dimethoxy-	55	151°	C ₁₈ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₃ Cl	17.00	17.26
2-Chloro-	65	> 280°	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₃ Cl ₃	19.10	19.52
2-Hydroxy-	60	> 280°	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	21.50	21.77
2-Carboxy-	45	> 280°	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₃ Cl	18.25	18.54
2,4-Dimethyl-	50	203°	C ₁₈ H ₂₄ N ₃ Cl	24.85	24.87

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